

Linear Free Energy Relationships in Solid State Reactions. Part-IV. Addition Reactions of Cobalt Chloride with *p*-Substituted-anilines

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THE correlation of the substituent parameters with the kinetic data in the solid-solid reactions between acetates of cobalt and zinc with substituted-aniline hydrochlorides has already been established¹. In these reactions $\text{MX}_2 \cdot 2$ amine complexes are formed and the stronger acid replaces the weaker one to liberate acetic acid along with the attachment of amine to the metal in a concerted step. The rate and energy of activation data was found to correlate satisfactorily with substituent parameters.

Different complexes, $\text{CoX}_2 \cdot 2$ amine ($\text{X} = \text{OCH}_3$, CH_3 , Cl , Br and I) have been prepared from the solution phase and characterised by spectrochemical methods². The amine adducts of cobalt halides are usually prepared from solution phase which is time consuming and requires large quantities of solvent and wastage of reagents. Here we report a new method for their synthesis in which the products can be obtained in quantitative yields by mixing the solid reactants in exact stoichiometric composition to get the pure compounds. The present investigation aims at studying the applicability of Hammett's equation to another class of reactions, i.e. addition reactions.

Experimental

Cobalt chloride (G.R., Loba) was dried at 140° for 7 h to get the anhydrous sample. The anhydrous sample was analysed for cobalt content volumetrically³ (Found: 44.7. Calcd. 45.4%). *p*-Methoxy, *p*-methyl, *p*-chloro and *p*-iodoanilines were purified by repeated recrystallisation from water; *p*-bromoaniline (G.R., Fluka) was used as such. The m.p.s. of the compounds were 57.0, 43.5, 70.0, 65.0 and 67.5° for *p*- OCH_3 , *p*- CH_3 , *p*- Cl , *p*- Br and *p*- I anilines respectively, which agreed with the values given in literature⁴. The compounds were sieved and particles of size $< 42 \mu\text{m}$ were collected for kinetic studies.

The reflectance spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer using magnesium oxide as reference material, infrared spectra (KBr) on a Pye-Unichem SP3-300 spectrophotometer. Magnetic moment studies were done on a Gouy balance. Tlc was done using benzene-methanol (1 : 3) as eluent.

The melting or eutectic points of the compounds/mixtures were determined in order to select the temperature for kinetic studies. The kinetics were

studied at temperature below the melting point of the lowest melting mixture. The colour of the products varies from light blue to dark blue and is distinctly different from that of cobalt chloride (violet) and the anilines (white). The kinetics were therefore studied by measuring the change in the thickness of the product boundary formed at the interface of the reactants as a function of time in a capillary⁵. Glass capillaries (i.d. 0.3 cm) and a travelling microscope with least count of 0.002 cm were used for the studies. The reaction of *p*-iodoaniline is very slow at the temperature at which the other reactions were studied and therefore its kinetics were studied at a higher temperature.

The products from the solid state were prepared by intimately mixing the reactants in 1 : 2 stoichiometric mixtures. The mixture was kept in a thermostat (308 K) for 48 h to get the final product. The products were also prepared from solution phase reaction by the method reported in literature.

Results and Discussion

The solid-solid reactions of cobalt chloride with substituted-anilines give products of stoichiometry $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot (4\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{OCH}_3$, CH_3 , Br , Cl and I . The solid and solution phase reaction products were analysed for Co, Cl, C, H and N, and the results show that the products are of composition $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2(4\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)$.

In infrared spectra, free primary amines exhibit NH stretching vibrations near 3500 cm^{-1} , but in compounds in which a primary amine is coordinated to a metal atom the NH band shifts to $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ir spectra of the solid state reaction products has absorption between 3300 and 3200 cm^{-1} assignable to coordinated primary amine. The spectra of solid and solution phase products are superimposable. No peaks corresponding to unreacted amine are observed in any of the products.

In octahedral complexes of cobalt(II) usually one band is seen in the visible region ($\sim 560 \text{ nm}$) and in tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes the absorption in the visible region is observed at around 640 nm . The reflectance spectra of the solid and solution phase reaction products show only one band in the visible region at about 640 nm . The magnetic moment for the complexes lie in the range $4.4\text{--}4.8 \text{ B.M.}$, which are also typical for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complex. The reflectance spectra for solid and solution phase products are identical.

The tlc of the solid and solution phase products show that pure products are formed, as the chromatogram reveals a single spot. The R_f values for the solid phase and solution phase reaction products are identical. The elemental and spectral data for the solid and solution phase products are summarised in Table 1. On the basis of the above results it can be concluded that pure tetrahedral $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2(4\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)$ aniline complexes are formed as the only solid products in these reactions.

NOTES

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA FOR SOLID STATE REACTION PRODUCTS OF COBALT(II) CHLORIDE WITH SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES

Substituent	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)					μ_{eff} B M	λ_{max} nm	ν_{max} cm^{-1}
	C	H	N	Co	Cl			
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	42.87 (44.65)	4.70 (4.76)	6.48 (7.44)	15.00 (15.68)	18.86 (18.87)	4.46	637	3200, 3225
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	46.23 (48.84)	5.10 (5.23)	9.10 (8.14)	17.13 (17.15)	20.86 (20.64)	4.89	637	3275, 3295
<i>p</i> -Cl	35.43 (37.40)	3.00 (3.17)	5.31 (7.27)	15.41 (15.32)	17.65 (18.44)	4.87	637	3290, 3300
<i>p</i> -Br	28.02 (30.36)	2.50 (2.53)	4.91 (3.91)	12.26 (12.45)	19.61 (19.98)	4.57	635	3278, 3225
<i>p</i> -I	40.30 (41.37)	3.00 (3.45)	8.00 (8.05)	16.47 (16.95)	20.32 (20.40)	4.67	637	3270, 3220

The kinetics were studied at temperature much below the melting points of the reactants or of any of their possible eutectic mixtures. The kinetic data follow the rate law,

$$\xi^2 = kt + c$$

where ξ is the thickness of the colored product layer at time t , and k and c are constants. The plot of ξ^2 vs t for these reactions is linear. The anilines diffuse through the product layer and cobalt chloride lattice to react and then form the products as shown by the marker experiment, in which the position of the boundary was marked and direction of penetration of either of the reactants was studied with time. The values of energies of activation for these reactions as determined from Arrhenius plot are 24.6, 29.3, 52.8, 56.6 and 67.3 kJ mol⁻¹ for X=OCH₃, CH₃, Cl, Br and I respectively. Thus the reactivity order of different substituents is 4-OCH₃ > 4-CH₃ > 4-Cl > 4-Br > 4-I. The observed difference in reactivity may either be due to a difference in the rates of diffusivities of the reactants, which leads to lesser concentration of amine at the reaction site or due to difference in rates of reactions from one reactant to the other when they come sufficiently close to each other. The relative sizes of 4-chloro-, 4-bromo-, 4-methyl- and 4-methoxyanilines are approximately similar, while the iodo substituent is much bulkier, which decreases the rate of diffusion as also the effective area of contact between the reactants resulting in a higher E_a value.

Significant contribution from vapour phase diffusion, bulk diffusion etc., to these reactions is ruled out because they involve much larger energies of activation at the temperatures at which these reactions have been studied. This is further supported by the observation that no significant growth of the product boundary was observed when the reactants were placed in a capillary and separated by an air-gap of 3 cm. In case of 4-CH₃ and 4-OCH₃ initially a product boundary was formed, but its thickness did not vary appreciably with time.

Thus the only plausible transportation of the aniline molecules to the reaction zone is mainly by surface migration and by grain boundary diffusion through pores and cracks which develop during the reaction due to difference in sizes of reactants and products.

To test the correlation of the measured energy of activation data with the substituent parameters, the Hammett substitution constants used are σ_p , σ_I , σ_R and σ^+ . σ_p denotes substituent constants for *p*-substituted compounds σ_I and σ_R are its inductive and resonance components respectively, and σ^+ is electrophilic substituent constant. Values of these constants were obtained from literature⁶. The best correlation of the energy of activation data was found with σ_p (Fig. 1), all others gave a poor fit (Table 2). The substituent effect is thus transmitted to the reaction centre both by resonance and inductive effects. The value of reaction constant is 44.0 kJ mol⁻¹ and the electron-withdrawing groups decrease the rate whereas electron donors favour the reaction as expected.

The heats of addition of two molecules of gaseous amines to the anhydrous crystalline cobalt

Fig. 1. Plot of Hammett constant σ against energy of activation for reactions of cobalt chloride with substituted anilines by capillary technique.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF ENERGY OF ACTIVATION VALUES AGAINST SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS

Substituent parameters	Corr. coeff.	Slope	Intercept
σ_p	0.9967	43.96	79.81
σ_p^+	0.8423	55.07	46.42
σ_I	0.6582	27.88	68.81
σ_R	0.6118	69.37	87.00

halides are almost independent of the substituents in the benzene nucleus of anilines (179.7–193.2 kJ mol⁻¹) for X=H, 4-CH₃, 4-Cl, 4-Br and 4-OCH₃.⁷ The observed systematic variations of E_a values with substituent parameters show that the reactivity in the solid state reactions is dependent on the changes in the electronic effects of the substituents as have been previously observed in the solid state reactions of zinc and cobalt acetate with aniline hydrochlorides¹.

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Spin-trapping of Free Radical Intermediates formed during the Photo-oxidation of Aldehydes and Ketones by Hexachloro Palladate(IV) and Iridate(IV) Ions

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THE use of radical addition reactions to detect short-lived radical intermediates was first proposed by Janzen in 1965¹. Since then this technique for which Janzen and Blackburn² coined the name 'spin-trapping' has been developed extensively³. The recent surge in interest in the long established problem of photoreduction of platinum group metal salts⁴ has prompted us to report a detail spin-

trapping and matrix isolation epr study of photo-oxidation of various alcohols by hexachlorometalate(IV) ions (M=Pt, Pd and Ir)⁶. In this communication, the initial results of the photo-oxidation of some aldehydes (formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and propionaldehyde) and ketones (acetone, methyl ethyl ketone and diethyl ketone) by hexachloro palladate(IV) and iridate(IV) ions have been reported.

Experimental

The details of the epr spin-trapping experiments are the same as described earlier^{6,8}. α -Phenyl-tert-butyl nitron (PBN) and sodium-2-sulphanatophenyl-tert-butyl nitron (SPBN) (Aldrich) were used as spin-trapping agents in neat organic and aqueous organic substrate solutions respectively. 18-Crown-6(1,4,7,10,13,16-hexaoxacyclo-octadecane) was added to the solution in pure organic substrates to solubilise the inorganic salts. Aldehydes and ketones (B.D.H.) were used as such except formaldehyde, which was purified⁷ to remove the traces of methyl alcohol.

Results and Discussion

The free radical intermediates produced in these photo-redox reactions react with either of the spin-traps (PBN or SPBN) to produce the corresponding spin adducts. The epr spectra (Fig. 1) of nitroxides, the spin adducts thus produced, exhibit the characteristic primary main triplet due to ¹⁴N and the secondary doublet splittings due to β -hydrogen. The magnitudes of the hyperfine splitting parameters of the different spin adducts (Table 1) suggest that the carbon-centred free radicals are formed in these reactions. This can be attributed to the direct attack of the photo-excited hexachlorometalate(IV)

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of spin adducts of CH₂CHO with (upper) PBN obtained on the photolysis of (PdCl₆)²⁻ in neat acetaldehyde solution and with (lower) SPBN obtained on the photolysis of (IrCl₆)²⁻ in 50% aqueous acetaldehyde solution.